

SHORT FIBRE POLYAMIDE UNDER COMBINED SHEAR AND TENSILE LOADING: A NON-DESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION OF MICRO DAMAGE EVOLUTION

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ABSTRACT

The following paper focuses on the evolution of micro damage in short fibre reinforced polyamide. Therefore, tube samples are subjected to uni- and biaxial fatigue loadings. The evolution of micro damage is analysed by the non-destructive method of X-ray refraction analysis with consideration of the fibre orientation distribution. For validation of the applied micro damage models, fractographic analyses are performed.

Concluding some general results, it has been observed that the load ratio influences the quantitative dominance of micro damage, whereas occurring damage phenomena depend on the type of loading (i.e. tension and torsion). Thus, zones in the Haigh-diagram are detected, where the occurrence of damage mechanisms qualitatively and quantitatively changes. This is a basis for further research regarding anisotropic damage criteria.

1 INTRODUCTION

The increasing use of short fibre reinforced polyamide in automotive applications is caused by good light weight properties, recyclability and cost efficient large volume production by injection moulding. The knowledge of the anisotropic behaviour regarding strength, stiffness, fatigue and damage as well is indispensable for an effective design process and the application in safety related components.

In this presentation the micro damage evolution of short fibre reinforced polyamide caused by tension, torsion and tension-torsion fatigue loading is discussed. For that purpose injection moulded tube samples of polyamide 6 with 30 wt% of short glass fibres and a high degree of fibre orientation in the length direction are used (B3WG6, BASF). The fibre orientation, which has a significant influence on the damage behaviour, is simulated in the design process and experimentally confirmed by high resolution computed tomography (μ CT) and X-ray refraction analysis. Since the non-destructive method of X-ray refraction analysis allows for the directional detection of inner surfaces in materials where the electron density changes, it is applied for the measurement of fibre orientation and damage evolution as well. With the knowledge of the refraction behaviour of bonded and unsoldered fibres, fibre end faces and matrix cracks as well as some additional information about the composite like fibre volume fraction, fibre orientation and fibre length distribution, it is possible to separate the damage mechanisms debonding of fibre and matrix and micro cracking in the matrix material. Accompanying fractographic analyses are performed to validate the applied micro damage models.

2 THEORY

2.1 Damage mechanisms in short fibre reinforced composites

In general the micro damage of short fibre reinforced thermoplastics is ascribed to the mechanisms of debonding between fibres and matrix, micro cracking in the matrix material and fibre fracture. The occurrence of debonding or fracture of fibres highly depends on the fibre length. The application of

micromechanical models like [1] by Bowyer and Bader allows for calculation of the critical fibre length: Shorter fibres are debonded from the matrix, whereas longer fibres are broken.

Due to the fracture of fibres in the manufacturing process, the fibre end faces are free of facing and often already debonded in the undamaged state. Under mechanical loading these imperfections are initial locations for micro damage like fibre matrix debonding and matrix micro cracking. Caused by increasing loads or load cycles an accumulation of micro damage phenomena is detected, that lead to an incipient crack and subsequently to final damage.

2.2 X-ray refraction analysis

The method of X-ray refraction analysis is based on the X-ray optic effect of refraction on surfaces of different refractive indices [2]. The scattering angles are below half a degree hence, a small angle X-ray scattering setup is used. The Kratky-collimated X-ray beam (Mo-K α , $\lambda = 0.7 \text{ \AA}$, square section = $(2 \times 0.05) \text{ mm}^2$) passes the sample. The intensity of refraction I_R is measured at a fixed scattering angle, the absorption I_A is measured indirectly by a scattering foil. These intensities as well as their zero values I_{A0} and I_{R0} , measured without a sample in the path of rays, lead to the refraction value C (eq. 1), which represents the plane projection of inner surfaces of the radiographed volume as a function of the material thickness d .

$$C = \left[\frac{I_R/I_{R0}}{I_A/I_{A0}} - 1 \right] \cdot d^{-1} \quad (1)$$

Describing the absorption by Lambert-Beer-Law leads to the specific refraction value C/μ which is independent of the material thickness. Due to the homogeneous distribution of inner surfaces in the PA6 GF30 the mean value C_m of a representative volume is used.

Glass fibres that are acting like cylindrical lenses cause an oriented X-ray expansion vertical to the fibre axis. The refraction value of a unidirectional roving as a function of the angle Θ between the collimation plane and the fibre axis is proportional to a $\cos^2(\Theta)$ -function. Therefore, The orientation of short fibres can be measured by X-ray refraction topography [3], [4] if the refraction behaviour of the fibre end faces and the semi crystalline matrix is determined [5]. For that purpose the refraction behaviour of a fibre roving and the end faces is measured (eq. 2). Due to fracture of glass fibres in the manufacturing process of injection moulding, the end faces are statistically oriented and cause an isotropic refraction value that is considered by the factor A .

$$f(\theta) = \frac{C_m(\theta)}{C_{m,max}} = A + (1 - A) \cdot \cos^2(\theta) \quad (2)$$

Furthermore, the refraction behaviour of the matrix material is measured by an unreinforced PA6 sample. For the occurring strains this offset is constant. Connecting $f(\theta)$ to the elliptic frequency distribution of the fibre orientation, measured by μ CT, the distribution function of the fibre orientation is given by (eq. 3). C_1 and C_2 include information about the constant refraction offsets of the matrix and the production-related debonded fibre end faces as well as information about the fibre orientation in the material. They can be determined by measuring $C_m(\theta=0^\circ)$ and $C_m(\theta=90^\circ)$.

$$F(\theta) = C_m(\theta) = C_1 \cdot \cos^2(\theta) + C_2 \quad (3)$$

Progressive damage in short fibre reinforced composites occurs as debonding of fibres and matrix micro-cracking and results in an increase of the refraction value [6]–[8]. The refraction behaviour of the damaged state is characterised by a $\cos^2(\Theta)$ -function, too. The degree of fibre matrix debonding $\varphi(\Theta)$ is described as (eq. 4). In this respect, account is only taken to the refraction values that correspond to the fibre claddings ($C_m \hat{}$).

$$\varphi(\theta) = \frac{C_{m, \text{damaged}}'(\theta) - C_{m, \text{undamaged}}'(\theta)}{C_{m, 100\% \text{ debonded}}'(\theta) - C_{m, \text{undamaged}}'(\theta)} \quad (4)$$

If the micro damage behaviour only contains fibre matrix debonding, the degree of fibre matrix debonding is a function of Θ . If also matrix cracking is involved into the damage process, the degree of fibre matrix debonding is assumed to remain constant regarding Θ . On the one hand, this assumption is necessary for the separation of damage phenomena, on the other hand this assumption is approximately confirmed by fractographic analysis.

The refraction behaviour of matrix cracks is described as refraction triggering ring segments which are stringed together [9], comparable to the refraction behaviour of fibre claddings. Assuming the orientation of matrix cracks as perpendicular ($\theta=90^\circ$) to the principal direction of fibre orientation, no refraction signal, caused by matrix micro cracking is measured in the $\theta=0^\circ$ measurement. Therefore, the refraction ratio, caused by fibre matrix debonding can be calculated from the $\theta=0^\circ$ measurement. Accordingly, the refraction ratio of matrix-micro cracking is also known and the measured refraction value in the damages state can be split into the corresponding parts (eq. 5).

$$C_{m, \text{damage}} = C_{m, \text{matrix}} + C_{m, \text{fibre end faces}} + C_{m, \text{fibre cladding}}(\theta) + C_{m, \text{debonding}}(\theta) + C_{m, \text{matrix crack}}(\theta) \quad (5)$$

The density of inner surfaces of matrix micro cracking is given as:

$$S_M = C_{m, \text{matrix crack}}(90^\circ) \cdot \frac{2^\circ}{180^\circ} \cdot \frac{(\rho_{\text{fibre}} - \rho_{\text{matrix}})^2}{\rho_{\text{matrix}}^2} \cdot \frac{S_F}{(C_{m, \text{fibre cladding}}(0^\circ) + C_{m, \text{fibre cladding}}(90^\circ))} \quad (6)$$

with the mass densities ρ , the interfacial density of the fibre cladding S_F and the factor $2^\circ/180^\circ$ for the conversion from the isotropic to anisotropic refraction behaviour [5], [9].

3 MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

3.1 Material and Test Samples

The analysed material is a polyamide 6 with 30 wt% of short glass fibres (PA6GF30). By thermal extraction and microscopic analysis, the geometry of the fibres is measured. The fibre lengths are Weibull-distributed in a range from 20 μm to 800 μm , with a mean fibre value of 180 μm . The mean fibre diameter is about 10.4 μm . The glass transition range, measured by dynamic-mechanical-analysis, is between 46 $^\circ\text{C}$ and 98 $^\circ\text{C}$, with a glass transition temperature of 72 $^\circ\text{C}$. The fibre orientation frequency is simulated in the design process and experimentally measured by X-ray refraction analysis and high resolution computed tomography. With a fibre orientation value of $a_{zz}=0.9\pm 1.4\%$ (X-ray refraction analysis) a high degree of fibre orientation in the length direction of the sample is reached. The tilting of fibres in the direction of thickness is negligible. For analysing the damage behaviour of PA6GF30 caused by uni- and biaxial fatigue loading, tube samples are used [10].

Figure 1: injection moulded, short fibre reinforced tube sample PA6GF30 (Θ angle of rotation between z-axis and collimation plane of the X-ray).

3.2 Experimental Setup

For the qualitative and quantitative analysis of micro damage phenomena in PA6GF30 the tube samples are fatigued by constant load amplitude experiments with the load ratios of $R=0.1$ and $R=-1$. The biaxial ratio is described as:

$$\beta = \frac{S_{zz}/R_{m,zz}}{S_{\varphi z}/R_{m,\varphi z}}; \beta = 1 \quad (7)$$

with the fatigue loads S and the static strengths R_m . The axial and torsion strains are measured by the optic and contactless system Aramis (by Co. GOM). To avoid thermal heating, a load frequency of 2 Hz is used and the testing climate is adapted to a surfaces temperature of 23 ± 3 °C. The climate conditions are below the glass transition zone, 23 °C and a humidity state of dry as moulded. After fixed numbers of load cycles the evolution of micro damage is measured by accompanying X-ray refraction analysis with different orientation angles Θ between the fibre length axis and the collimation plane of the X-ray. Fractographic analyses are performed to qualitatively confirm the presence of the assumed damage phenomena.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the following section the results regarding the evolution of micro damage in short fibre reinforced polyamide 6 are shown. The focus is placed on uni- and biaxial fatigue loads with a load ratio of $R=0.1$. Firstly, the occurring micro damage is optically analysed by means of fractography, the results are shown in figure 2. In the analysed material fibre fracture is determined to be a subordinate phenomenon. That confirms the micro mechanic analysis regarding the critical fibre length. The uniaxial tension fatigue load (figure 2a) causes fibre matrix debonding and matrix micro cracking. For the debonding, starting at unsoldered fibre end faces, a specific correlation between the fibre orientation, the direction of load and the degree of fibre matrix debonding is not detected. Likewise, matrix micro cracks mostly start at debonded fibre end faces but their orientation is preferentially vertical to the direction of load (z -direction). In regions with a high density of unsoldered fibres and matrix micro cracks, meso-cracks are formed that proceed from fibre to fibre. In this process fibres preferentially bridge the cracks, seldom, fibres are broken. In figure 2b the micro damage of a torsion loaded sample is shown. In this case, the micro damage is assigned to fibre matrix debonding, starting at debonded fibre end faces. Matrix micro cracking is not detected. Looking at the damage of the combined axial-torsion loaded sample in figure 2c, unsoldered fibres as well as matrix micro cracks are observed. The qualitative behaviour is comparable to the axial loaded sample.

Secondly, the non-destructive method of X-ray refraction is applied for measuring the evolution of micro damage. Comparing the increase of the refraction values of axial, torsion and axial-torsion fatigue loads in figure 3, a distinct increase in the first 10 % of lifetime is observable. This marks the initiation of micro damage. After the first phase of damage initiation a nearly linear accumulation of damage with the normalised lifetime is measured in the second phase. The qualitative progress of inner surfaces, described by a power function, is the same for the applied uni- and biaxial loads. Regarding quantity significant differences are detected: Whereas the 90° -measurements of the axial and the axial-torsion loaded tests show well comparable results regarding the increase of inner surfaces and the final maximum value ($\Delta C_{m, max} \approx 95$ %), the torsion load causes a considerable lower level of ΔC_m in the 90° -measurement ($\Delta C_{m, max} \approx 55$ %). In phase 2 the gradient of damage accumulation is noticeable lesser than in the axial and axial-torsion loaded tests. Looking at the 0° -measurements the torsion and the axial-torsion fatigue tests cause a more similar evolution of micro damage ($\Delta C_{m, max} \approx 25$ %) than the axial load ($\Delta C_{m, max} \approx 15$ %).

Figure 2: Fractographic analysis of the damage phenomena of fatigue loaded PA6 GF30.

Figure 3: Damage accumulation in fatigue tests: Evolution of the refraction value with respect to lifetime. Fitting function: $\Delta C_m(N/N_F) = A_1 \cdot (N/N_F)^{A_2}$

For separating damage phenomena the present model (section 2.2) is applied. Independently from the applied load the refraction value is proportional to a $\cos^2(\Theta)$ -function and can be described by the refraction values of the 0° - (parallel) and the 90° -measurement (vertical). Figure 4 exemplarily shows the ratios of the refraction behaviour in the damaged and in the undamaged state and their separation into the damage mechanisms of fibre matrix debonding and matrix micro cracking. The model includes the following assumptions:

- The refraction behaviour of the debonded fibre end faces and the matrix material is constant,
- the fibre orientation frequency is known,
- the degree of fibre matrix debonding is independent from the fibre orientation and
- matrix micro cracking occurs in a vertical direction to the preferred orientation of the fibres.

Figure 4: Exemplary representation of micro damage phenomena fibre matrix debonding and matrix micro cracking (tensile fatigue test $R=0.1$).

Figure 5: Degree of fibre matrix debonding over the scanning angle Θ : Last measured damage state of fatigue loading experiments ($R=0.1$).

If the micro damage only comprises fibre matrix debonding, the degree of fibre matrix debonding may change with the angle of fibre orientation. This is shown in figure 5. The degree of fibre matrix debonding is defined in the range from 0 % to 100 %. Exemplarily, 10 % of fibre matrix debonding means that either ten of hundred fibres are completely unsoldered or 10 % of the fibre cladding of each fibre is unsoldered. Additionally, each state between is possible. The increase of the refraction value due to torsion fatigue loading is fully described by fibre matrix debonding. However, in the cases of axial and axial-torsion loading the entire increase of refraction cannot be interpreted solely by debonding of fibres. There must also appear additional phenomena like matrix micro cracking. This is

confirmed by the fractographic analyses (figure 2).

Regarding the damage due to torsion fatigue loading it is visible, that the fibres in 90°-direction are highly affected by fibre matrix debonding ($\varphi(90^\circ)=94\%$), whereas the 0°-fibres are considerably lesser effected ($\varphi(0^\circ)=12\%$). Considering the fibre orientation frequency, in 0°-direction many fibres are affected by debonding to a lesser extent, whereas in the 90°-direction about one-tenth of the number of fibres is highly affected by debonding.

Figure 6: Evolution of strains with respect to the normalised lifetime in load controlled fatigue tests with a load ratio of $R=0.1$.

Looking at the evolution of strains in the load controlled fatigue test with a load ratio of $R=0.1$, figure 6 shows that the mean strains increase, whereas the strain amplitudes stay constant with respect to lifetime. The dynamic stiffness remains constant and cannot be applied for a damage-equivalent. The strain is split into a linear elastic part and a non-linear elastic part (8). The non-linear elastic strain, mathematically described by a creep strain approach (9), includes the viscoelastic and plastic behaviour of the matrix material as well as the evolving micro damage. The L_{mi} are the applied axial and torsion mean stresses respectively. In the following, the non-linear elastic strain is applied for a damage-equivalent indicator.

$$s_{mi}(t) = s_{mi, \text{elastic}} + s_{mi, \text{non-linear elastic}}(t) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{mi} = \varepsilon_{zz}, \gamma_{\varphi z} \quad (8)$$

$$s_{mi, \text{non-linear elastic}}(t) = k_1 \cdot L_{mi}^{k_2} \cdot \left(\frac{N}{N_F \cdot f}\right)^{k_3} \quad \text{with} \quad L_{mi} = \sigma_{m,zz}, \tau_{m,\varphi z} \quad (9)$$

In figure 7 the damage phenomena fibre matrix debonding and matrix micro cracking are plotted to the non-linear elastic strains. A linear correlation passing the coordinate origin is shown. Hence, damage accumulation starts with the non-linearity of the strain. Comparing the case of axial loading (figure 7a) to the case of combined axial-torsion loading (figure 7b), the maximum density of inner surfaces due to matrix micro cracking is identical but the degree of fibre matrix debonding is considerably higher for the biaxial loading. This reflects the influence of torsion. The maximum values of micro damage are summarised in table 1.

Figure 7: Evolution of the damage mechanisms fibre matrix debonding and matrix micro cracking over the normalised non-linear elastic strain.

load	degree of fibre matrix debonding ϕ [%]	density of matrix micro cracking S_m [mm ⁻¹]
axial	7.2	0.5
torsion	32.7*	-
axial-torsion	11.4	0.5

Table 1: Maximum values of micro damage (* the integral mean value is used).

Additionally, all the mechanical loading tests were performed with the load ratio of $R=-1$. The occurring micro damage phenomena, detected by fractographic analysis, are qualitatively the same for the corresponding loads. The increase of the refraction value with respect to the lifetime is qualitatively comparable to figure 3. Quantitatively, the micro damage is considerably lesser. Furthermore, the mean strains, as well as the strain amplitudes remain constant, so they cannot be applied for a damage-equivalent indicator.

In the following the key results of the analysis of damage evolution are summarised. Schematically, they are shown in figure 8. The phenomenon of matrix micro cracking only arises in combination with axial tension loads. In contrast, fibre matrix debonding arises independently from the applied load. The significance of micro damage for the final damage is higher, if the mean load is unequal to zero. In the case of biaxial loading the micro damage shows an overall slightly higher degree of micro damage, than the uniaxial cases. Furthermore, for load cases with non-zero mean stresses a linear correlation between the damage evolution and the non-linear elastic strain is detected. Hence, the strain evolution for load cases without mean stresses is different the non-linear elastic strain is solely a measure but not the reason for micro damage.

Figure 8: Schematic 3D Haigh-diagram with key results of the analysis of micro damage due to uniaxial and biaxial fatigue loads.

5 CONCLUSION

The present paper deals with the evolution of micro damage in short glass fibre reinforced polyamide 6. Therefore, uniaxial and biaxial fatigue tests are performed and the damage evolution is measured non-destructively by X-ray refraction analysis. A model, that includes the fibre orientation frequency, is applied for separation of the damage phenomena fibre matrix debonding and matrix micro cracking. Fractographic analyses verify the results from the non-destructive testing.

The study reveals that the dominance of micro damage depends on the load ratio in the fatigue tests. Load cases with non-zero mean stresses cause higher degrees of micro damage. Furthermore, the occurring damage phenomena depend on the applied load: Axial tensile loads cause matrix micro cracking, whereas fibre matrix debonding occurs under axial, torsion and axial-torsion loadings. Moreover, for load cases with non-zero mean stresses a linear correlation between the damage phenomena and the non-linear elastic strains is detected.

The present study provides fundamental knowledge about the evolution of micro damage caused by uniaxial and biaxial mechanical loadings that can be prospectively used for improving damage models and differentiating damage and fatigue damage criteria.

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